

Housing and Sustainable Health Status in Rivers State

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Abstract

The study, housing and sustainable health status in Rivers State, was designed in line with the survey research. The objective of this study was to examine the relationship between housing and sustainable health status in Rivers State. The scope of this study was limited to Bori in Khana Local Government Area of Rivers State. The population consisted of all tenants (micro-unit of analysis). This study conveniently adopted a sample size of 180 respondents. The spearman Rank correlation coefficient (ρ) and the mean/standard deviation were the statistical tool for testing of hypothesis and analyzing the research questions respectively using the statistical packages for social sciences (SPSS). Findings revealed that there was a significant relationship between habitability and quality of building. Freedom from crowding did not necessarily lead to disease prevention and control. The study concluded that healthy environment promotes sound health. The study recommended that there should be minimum standard requirements for landlords and tenants before habitation.

Keywords: housing, sustainable, health status.